

TECHNOLOGIES OF SPEECH DEVELOPMENT IN SPASTIC FORMS OF CHILDREN'S CEREBRAL PALSY

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Annotation: *Any psychological impact on a child with a speech impediment should be aimed not only at correcting the stage left behind, but also at preventing backwardness and paving the way for harmonious development.*

Key words: *mental difficulties, psychological diagnostics, developmental laws, educational process.*

Voluntary attention to speech is less important than involuntary attention. This is due to the weakness of the internal brakes and the obvious organization braking. A difficult-to-manage organization leads to instability when there is a lack of braking speech. Distribution of attention in speech defects, difficult distribution of transitions is due to the fragility of braking and propulsion processes. When raising children with speech impediments, the court should consider the types of higher nervous activity.

The following are some guidelines for developing psychological correction programs for children with speech impediments:

1. The principle of systematization of corrective, preventive and developmental issues
2. The principle of unity of correction and psychological diagnostics
3. The principle of the primacy of causal correction
4. The principle of corrective action
5. The principle of taking into account the psychological and individual characteristics of a person with a speech impediment
6. The principle of complexity of methods of psychological influence

The principle of systematization of corrective, preventive and developmental issues states that there are 3 types of issues in any correctional work, i.e.

- 1) correction,

- 2) prophylactic and
- 3) developer.

This means that there are interdependencies and inconsistencies in the overall development of the child's personality. In other words, every child is at a different stage of development, that is, a very high level of development is normal, a low level means that there are mental difficulties in development. This leads to the law of uneven development. The slowing down of certain aspects of personality development can lead to mental retardation or other difficulties in the development of a child with a speech impediment. For example, as a result of the slow development of cognitive and reading motives, the child's logical operational intelligence lags behind. Therefore, when corrective development programs identify issues and goals, it is necessary to use not only current problems, but also short-term development forecasts.

In short, a correctional development program should perform 3 tasks:

Correction of correction and lag correction.

Prophylaxis is the early detection of deterioration and lag.

Developer - a focus on enriching, optimizing the content of development.

Taking these 3 programs together can give the expected results.

Principles of psychological correction

The principle of unity of correction and psychological diagnostics reflects the fact that the work of a speech pathologist as a practical defectologist is a separate, integrated process of development and psychological support.

The principle of predominance of causal correction There are two types of correction: symptomatic and causal. While symptomatic correction is aimed at eliminating the external signs of these developmental difficulties, causal correction is aimed at eliminating the causes of these problems. The second type of correction should not lose its priority.

The theoretical foundations of the principle of correlation of activity are developed in the works of A.N. Leontev, D.B. Yelkonin. His focus is on the role of activity in a child's mental development.

The principle of taking into account the psychological and individual characteristics of the person with a speech impediment has a positive effect on the normative development of the mental and personal development of the person with a speech impediment.

It is important to note that taking into account the characteristics of children with speech impediments allows them to determine their own path.

The principle of involving close people in the social environment of a person with a speech impediment to correction recognizes that the mental development of a person with a speech impediment can be determined by the role of those around him. The child is assessed through interaction with the adults around him or her. After all, the child develops not in isolation from those around him, but together with them.

As a result of well-organized correctional work for children with speech disabilities, the potential of each child to focus on the learning process in an environment of social integration is constantly monitored by educators. 'gri is involved. This process increases the responsibility of children as a team to education, regardless of the degree to which they come from the classroom. Every child is a teacher of social, scientific and cultural education

According to the principle of programmed learning, programs that consist of a series of sequential treatments that form the necessary skills first by working with a speech pathologist and then independently are most effective.

The principle of gradual transition to complexity implies the gradual nature of correctional work. This principle helps a person with a speech impediment to enjoy what he or she is doing and to increase his or her interest in corrective work.

In the implementation of the correction program on the principle of taking into account the size and complexity of the given material, it is necessary to pay attention to the relative development of certain skills and abilities before giving a new volume of material.

The games, exercises, and material offered in accordance with the principle of taking into account the emotional complexity of the material should help to create a good emotional background. It is advisable that corrective exercises end with a positive emotional background.

Models of psychological correction

Before correcting a speech impediment, it is important to create a clear model of corrective action. They are: general, typical (usual), individual.

The general model of correction is that speech is a network of conditions derived from the development of an individual as a whole. It allows a person to be deeper, clearer, broader in his assumptions about the world around him, to be able to analyze and observe people, their relationships, changes in society, their activities. In this model of correction, the health of the person with a speech impediment and the time of training are clearly defined.

The typical (usual) model of correction is based on different bases of the organization of practical actions; to master the different components of action and to gradually shape different actions.

The individual form of correction takes into account the individual characteristics of the person with a speech impediment - such as his interests, mental development, learning abilities.

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